

CAMELINA SATIVA PROTOCOL FOR INTRODUCTION AS A SUMMER CATCH CROP IN FRANCE

INTRODUCTION

Camelina can be introduced as a summer intermediate catch crop in areas of Central Europe after harvesting the main crop such as winter cereals or peas. This rotation has been implemented in a pilot value chain in the northern half of France. The availability of early-maturing varieties allows harvesting of the crop in about 90 days. The present protocol for the introduction of camelina as a summer intermediate catch crop has been optimized within the UNTWIST project through three years of field experiments in Île de France.

FACTS

- **Common names:** Camelina, Leindotter, Gold of Pleasure, False Flax.
- **Scientific name:** *Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz
Family: Brassicaceae or Cruciferae.
- **Drought-resistant oil crop** with a yield potential of 2.5 t/ha.
- **Plant height:** 60 to 120 cm.
- **Pollinator friendly species.**
- **1000-seed weight:** 0.8 - 1.6 g.

ADVANTAGES

- **Conventional machinery for winter cereals.**
- **Easy implementation & low-input crop.**
- **Drought & frost tolerant.**
- **Catch crop.**
- **Pest & disease tolerant.**
- **Pivoting root** - soil structure improver.
- **Different cycle length varieties** are available.
- **Excellent crop in rotation with cereals.**

AGRONOMIC PROTOCOL KEY POINTS

PLOTS

Avoid easily waterlogged soils, with crust formation and pH less than 5.5 and greater than 8.5.

SOWING

Shallow sowing (1-2 cm) in rows (12.5-15 cm distance) on a plot without weeds or straw.

NUTRIENTS

Guarantee minimum nitrogen availability (40 kg N/ha).

HERBICIDES

Check residual herbicides (mainly ALS & PDS).

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SOWING	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sowing date: End of June - first two weeks of July; if possible 24-48 h after main crop harvest to benefit from residual soil humidity. ▪ Sowing rate: 8 kg/ha. ▪ Row sowing: 12.5-15 cm between rows. ▪ Sowing depth: Superficially ≈ 1 cm. Ensure a good seed-soil contact. ▪ Fertilization: Nitrogen availability after cereals (40 kg N/ha) or peas (20 kg N/ha).
WEEDS	<p>With a proper crop establishment, camelina competes well with weeds (allelopathic effect). Check the herbicides registered for narrowleaf control in your country.</p>
HARVEST	<p>Best at full maturity: 1st half of October, when the siliques turn from lemon yellow to brown.</p> <p>If needed cutting & swathing: September, when 75% of siliques turn from lemon yellow to brown.</p> <p>Combine setting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Select a program of a crop with small seeds. ▪ Raise the reel to the height of the first fruits (10-15 cm) and lower rpm. ▪ Set a proper relation between concave distance and cylinder revolutions to ensure an appropriate threshing. ▪ Be cautious with the airflow in the sieves to minimize seed losses.
POST-HARVEST	<p>Maximum moisture for storage: 8%.</p> <p>If an excess of moisture is detected in the harvested grain (symptom: heating), drying and cleaning is recommended.</p>

Sowing date, sowing rate and strategy as well as nitrogen fertilization rate was optimized in 3-year field trials within the **UNTWIST project**. The other parts of the protocol are based on previous experience with the crop and other projects and research work.

STAGES IN CAMELINA PRODUCTION

Photographs provided by Camelina Company.

